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Suturation of Trocar Site in Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy Patients

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ABSTRACT

Trocar site hernia has become a subject of interest in the literature with the widespread use of laparoscopic and robotic surgery. In this study, we aimed to compare the long-term results of patients after suturing the umbilical trocar site with polypropylene and polyglactin material in laparoscopic cholecystectomy cases performed in our hospital. With polypropylene suture, trocar site hernias can be reduced without an increase in the risk of chronic pain in the long term.

Introduction: Trocar site hernias (TSH) are important wound site problems encountered after laparoscopic and robotic surgery. To prevent TSH, suturing of the trocar site is frequently applied by surgeons. However, the preferred suture material varies from surgeon to surgeon and there is no consensus on the subject. This study aimed to compare the long-term results of suturing the umbilical trocar site with polypropylene suture (PpS) and polyglactin suture (PgS) in laparoscopic cholecystectomy cases, which is one of the most common laparoscopic procedures.

Materials and Methods: A total of 142 patients who underwent cholecystectomy for symptomatic cholelithiasis between March 2023 and December 2023 at Polatli Duatepe State Hospital were included in the study. Patients were divided into two groups according to the use of PpS and PgS in the suturing of the umbilical trocar site. Chronic pain at the wound site and TSH results were noted and compared. IBM SPSS Statistics v22 was used for statistical analysis. The chi-square test was used to compare categorical data.

Results: Of the 142 patients included in the study, PgS was used for suturing the umbilical trocar site in 87 and PpS was used in 55 patients. Pain persisting at the umbilical trocar site after the 1st postoperative month was seen in 6 patients in the PpS group and only in 1 patient in the PgS group ($p=0.014$). After 6 months of follow-up, TSH was seen in 6 patients in the PgS group and any patient in the PpS group ($p=0.049$). At the end of the 6-month follow-up, no statistically significant difference was observed in both groups in terms of chronic pain at the incision site (2 vs 0, $p=0.148$).

Discussion: With the widespread use of laparoscopic and robotic surgery, TSH has become an increasingly common problem. The American Hernia Society recommends suturing the umbilical trocar sites, especially if a 10 mm or wider trocar is used. However, there is not enough data in the literature regarding the suture material to be used.

Conclusion: It is possible to safely prevent TSH by using PPS in the repair of trocar sites after laparoscopic and robotic surgery.